

IMPROVEMENT OF PENETRATION RESISTANCE OF AMINE CURED EPOXY RESIN FOR CONCRETE LINING BY ION EXCHANGE ZEOLITE UNDER SULFURIC ACID

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Background (Corrosion Mechanisms of Concrete)

Concrete is widely used as a structural material in many applications around the world. However, concrete vessels and pipes particularly those used in wastewater treatment systems are indirectly affected by generation of hydrogen sulfide gas from the reduction of sulfates in the fluids by sulfate reducing bacteria [1].

Corrosion Mechanisms of Concrete under Sewage

□ Sulfate-reducing bacteria

□ Sulfur-oxidizing bacteria

Corrosion of Steel

Background (Corrosion Protection)

Definition of Resin lining

Thickness > 0.3 mm

Generally Resin Lining thickness
1.7mm~2.6mm

Resin for Lining

Epoxy, Vinyl ester, Unsaturated Polyester, Poly Urethane, etc.

Merit of Epoxy Resin Lining

Good adhesion properties
=> Easy surface treatment, Short Work time
Non Volatile solvent
=> Good working properties

Properties of Epoxy

Thermoset resin, excel in strength, heat resistance, adhesiveness and corrosion resistance than general thermoplastic resins, and even used as composite material for improvement of structural and functional property.

Hardener

Amines

Room temperature setting

Degraded by Acids

for Lining

Acid Anhydrides

High temperature setting

Degraded by alkali

Background (Degradation of Epoxy)

Studies of Corrosion Mechanism of Amine Cured Epoxy Resin Under Sulfuric Acid Solution

Amine cured epoxy resin is degraded in $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{aq}$

Amine react with $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{aq}$ to form salt

$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{aq}$ penetrate inside epoxy.

Studies of Corrosion Mechanism of Filler filled Amine Cured Epoxy Resin Under Sulfuric Acid Solution

- Increase of Corrosion Rate of the Material
=> Resin–filler interface, Dissolution of Filler

 Corrosion Inhibitor Filler ?

Background (Ion exchanger)

- Ion exchanger
 - Different separation, purification, and decontamination processes. The most common examples are water softening and water purification.

Zeolites

- Porous crystal
- Structure SiO_4 , AlO_4
- Cation

Inhibition of H^+ and OH^- by Ion exchanger

Zeolite and inorganic exchanger filler have ion exchange property. It is considered that ion exchange additives are possible to control the corrosion of resin.

Purpose

In this study, corrosion behavior and mechanism of EP/Amine filled inorganic ion exchanger in sulfuric acid environment was examined, and Effect of ion exchanger to corrosion of material Possibility of composite materials development designed to inhibition of corrosion were investigated.

Experimental Method (Test Materials)

Matrix Resin

Amine cured Epoxy Resin (E206s:Konishi Co., Ltd.)

Base resin : Bisphenol A Epoxy Hardener : Diamine Curing Agent

Filler

Cation Exchange Zeolite

Basic type (Na⁺ cation) (Zeorum 320NAA, Tosoh Corp.) => ZNa

Acidic type (H⁺ cation) (Zeorum 320HOA, Tosoh Corp.) => ZHS

General Filler

Alumina (Al /Nippon Light Metal Co., Ltd.) =>Al

Cation

Structure of Zeolite

Table Types and properties of fillers.

	320NAA	320HOA	Alumina
Mean diameter [μm]	6	6	4
Balk density [g/cm^3]	0.37	0.32	0.99
Pore size [\AA]	9	9	-
Cation [-]	Na ⁺	H ⁺	-

Experimental Method (Specimens)

Resin and filler were mixed
in volume ratio of 50:50 at
bulk density

Molded into 2mm thickness

Cured 24h at room temperature

Post cured 3h at 80C⁰

Cut into 60X25mm

Size of Specimen
Length 60mm Width
25mm thickness 2mm

Immersion test

10 mass % sulfuric acid
at 50⁰C.

Analytical method

Cross-section observation
Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)
Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometry (EDS)

The penetration depth of sulfur was calculated by:

$$X = (t_0 - t) / 2 \quad (1)$$

Where, X is penetration depth, t_0 is the total thickness of specimen before immersion, and t is that of the nominally non-penetrated part after immersion..

S element EDS mapping of cross section of specimens immersed in 10 mass% H₂SO₄ solutions after 24 hours.

Result (Penetration depth and rate)

Penetration rate of S element

	λ [mm/h ^{0.5}]
EP	9.57.E-2
ZHS	5.34.E-2
ZNa	7.73.E-2
Al	1.23.E-1

Comparison of “S” element penetration depth of all materials

Conclusion

The results confirm that addition of ion exchange materials to epoxy-amine resins can both improve the resistance of the material to sulfuric acid and reduce its diffusion rate. This demonstrates a potentially promising method for the control of biogenic sulfuric acid corrosion of concrete sewer pipes although care does need to be taken over the choice of filler material in order to optimize the performance of the lining system.

Reference

- [1]“Biological corrosion in the sewage system and the sewage treatment plant”, E. Stanaszek-Tomala, M. Fiertaka, Procedia Engineering, 161 (2016) 116-120

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